

Parental influence on academic performance of Home Economics students' in senior secondary students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines Parental Influence on Academic Performance of Home Economics Students' in Senior Secondary Students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State – Nigeria. The study seeks among others to investigate the influence of parents' socio-economic status on children's academic performance, to determine whether parents' educational status can influence students' academic performance and to investigate whether parents' occupational status can influence students' academic performance in the research area. Literature review was carried out to explore other authors' views on the topic. The study adopted a correlational research design and a total number of 1,840 students' participated in the study. Simple random sampling techniques was used and a well-structured five points Likert scale questionnaire and Home Economics Achievement Test (HEAT) were the main instruments used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using simple percentages merged with Mean and Standard deviation descriptive statistical tools. The result of the study revealed that low income of parent's is a major impediment to academic success and development in Home Economics on the part of the students. Additionally, students' academic performance in Home Economics is predicted by a chain of socio-economic factors resident in parent's and family network. The study recommended inter alia that; on the account of families of low socio-economic status who cannot afford to train their children properly in school, the government should increase the allocation of funds to provide for more amenities to facilitate learning in the school so that these poor student's will not lack basic amenities in the school.

Keywords: Academic performance; Home Economic; Parental influence; Socio-economic status; Students.

1. Introduction

Home environment has been conceptualized as the quality of human interactions from the point of view of the child. It includes those aspects that foster growth and development, such as family, trust and confidence, sharing of ideas, parents' support, parental approval, and siblings. Generally, children from low socio-economic status attend government schools, while children of well-to-do families attend private or public schools. These two types of schools have another major difference: differences in the medium of instruction (Soyibo, 2008).

In addition, home learning environment, school learning environment, and academic achievement may be influenced by various socio-economic factors like age, gender, family size, parents, education, and occupation, as well as by the socioeconomic status of the family. Thus, academic achievement is dependent on the school learning environment as well as the home learning environment. The present study is an attempt to investigate the parental influence on the academic performance of students. The focus will be on describing the key variables included in the study, i.e., parental influence and its impact on academic performance (James, 2014).

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Academic performance includes three processes: The ability to study and remember facts, being able to study effectively and see how facts fit together and form larger patterns of knowledge; being able to think for oneself about facts, and thirdly, being able to communicate knowledge verbally or on paper (Eduwen, 2010). Thus, performance might be seen as an index of the candidates' ability and motivation. A student's success is generally judged by examination performance (Journal of Education, 1981). Success in examination is a crucial indicator that a student has benefited from a course of study (Wiseman, 2008). Researchers believe that authentic academic performance should involve an examination of the total person; in other words, the examination should cover the individual's ability and skills in applying practical knowledge (Speete, 2002).

Parental influences have been identified as an important factor affecting students' achievement in Home Economics (Miller and Dryfoos, 2010). Child-rearing attitudes or parental behavior may be viewed in terms of many different dimensions, such as acceptance, affection, control, warmth, permissiveness, restrictiveness, and demanding behavior. Typically, warmth and control are thought to be the most important ways in which parents influence the development of their offspring or children (Maccoby & Martin, 2009) After Conducting extensive research, the studies of (Rohner 1986, 1981) reported major parenting dimensions in different human societies. These dimensions are parental control (permissiveness-strictness) and parental warmth (acceptance-rejection) (Rohner 1986, 1981).

Parenthood is neither a simple nor a very complicated process and is based on the perception and discharge of responsibilities in this phase of a parent's life. An Unbiased understanding of life by parents is very essential to raising or guiding children. Parents are the first teachers to their children. Parental influence may occur at different levels, ranging from simplistic tasks such as motivating children, being positive about school, or assisting children with their homework to more complicated and skill-demanding tasks such as assisting educators or the official management of schools, which demands higher skill levels (Khan, 2006).

This trend in socioeconomic status is posing huge problems to parents, governments, political parties, and stakeholders in education. Socio-economic status reinforces the activities and functioning of the teachers and students; it is revealed that the quality of parents and home background of a student goes a long way to predicting the quality and regularity of the satisfaction and provision of a child's functional survival and academic needs. Reduced parental care, with gross disregard for the social and economic needs of a child, usually results in poor academic performance in the child. On the other hand, where a child suffers parental and material deprivation and care due to divorce, death, or the absconding of one of the parents, the child's schooling may be affected as the mother/father (as the case may be) alone may not be financially buoyant to pay school fees, purchase books, and uniforms, and such a child may play truant, thus his performances in school may be adversely affected (Shittu, 2004), (Archibong 2020); and (Archibong, Ugbong, & Nsor, 2024).

According to the study of (Kelly 2016), good parenting supported by a strong economic home background could enhance the strong academic performance of the child. This further predicts academic performance when the child is properly counseled in the choice of his/her courses and vocation that matches his mental ability, interest, and capability whereas children under the care of illiterate mothers will find themselves roaming about the street laboring to make ends meet (Kelly, 2016). (Danesy & Okediran's 2002) in their views reported that street hawking among young school students has psychologically imposed other problems, like sex networking behavior, and juvenile delinquent behavior, which takes much of the student school time, thus instigating poor academic performance and dropout syndrome noticed amongst young school students. Still, they also reported that the maternal and paternal deprivation of the essential needs of the young students has prompted their poor performance in public examinations, such as JSSCE, WASC, and NECO (Danesy & Okediran, 2002).

(Coley 2002) study on the other hand identified three levels of parental socio-economic status as low, high, and medium socio-economic status. These statuses he reported have a tremendous effect on students' academic performance. According to him, socioeconomic status is often measured as a combination of education, income, and occupation. It is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group. When viewed through a social class lens, privilege, power, and control are emphasized (Coley, 2002).

Again, the study by Morgan et al. reported that children from low-socioeconomic-status households and communities tend to develop academic skills slowly as compared to children from higher Socioeconomic Status groups (Morgan, Farkas, Hillemeier, & Maczuga, 2009). Low-socioeconomic status communities are often under-resourced, negatively affecting students' academic progress (Aikens & Barbarin, 2008).

Also, inadequate education and increased dropout rates affect children's academic performance, a trend synonymous with the low- Socioeconomic Status groups of a community. Improving school systems and early intervention programs

may help to reduce these risk factors, and thus increased research on the correlation between Socioeconomic Status and education is essential (Maccoby & Martin, 2009).

This study examined Parental Influence on the academic performance of Home Economics Studies amongst Senior Secondary School Students in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State - Nigeria. The sample comprised of intermediate school students, and the age of the students was generally within the range of 14 to 18 years. The need to explain parent's role in the academic achievement of adolescents is imperative. However, this study wishes to understand the parental influences on students' academic success and performance.

1.1. Statement of the problem

The importance of education in an individual cannot be over-emphasized. Education has a long-lasting impact on one's life. The acquisition of knowledge and skills and all other worthwhile things that are transmitted to a person through formal and informal education determines his/her potential in the future.

At the end of every instructional period in school comes an examination. Over the years, society has been recording a persistent increase in the rate of poor performance in Home Economics in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE). If this trend is not nipped in the bud, it will have grave repercussions on the lives of these students, their parents, and society (Jegede 2000).

Comments from educators have shown that the blame for lack of good performance has been a result of neglect and carefree attitude towards academic work by students and parents. Home is the first school for a child where he/she is taught the basic norms and values by the parents before the child leaves for formal education. Contrary to the opinion that learning and reading begin in school, the first foundation of the child begins at home. A good and conducive home environment with adequate learning facilities would help to boost the intellectual and academic capability of the child. Well-educated parents would always have good attitudes towards education and provide learning materials such as television, instructional video tapes, novels, books, and journals that could facilitate the learning process (Caplow, 2000)

The motivation of any intelligent child towards learning is accelerated by the positive influence of his/her environment while others are negatively affected in terms of their non-stimulating home environment. Seeking answers to these problems constitutes a major problem of the research study.

1.2. Purpose of the study

The general purpose of this study was to find out Parental influence' on Academic Performance of Home Economic Students' in Senior Secondary Students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State – Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to:

- Investigate the influence of parents' socio-economic status and children's academic performance in Calabar Metropolis.
- Determine whether parents' educational status can influence students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis.
- Investigate whether parents' occupational status can influence students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis.

1.3. Justification of the study

Many experiential studies have been carried out on parental background and academic achievement on student in senior secondary school. Also, broad research has been done on the effect of parental socio economic status on students' academic performance in senior secondary schools by various researchers amongst whom are; (Hake 1999), (Ndubusi, 2005), (Craftetal, 2002), (Locke, 1970), (Mudock & Mudock, 2004), (Jersild, 2005) and (Archibong, Ugbong, & Nsor, 2024).

What could perhaps be new is the in-depth knowledge of the parental influence of Home Economics studies among senior secondary school students and their academic achievement. Consequently, the study sought to investigate the Parental Influence on Home Economics Studies among Senior Secondary School Students in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State - Nigeria.

Based on the above, this study is crucial for this reasons:

- It is anticipated that the findings of this study and its recommendations will aid parents to be up and doing in the upbringing of their children if they want them to be successful academically, socially and otherwise. This study will enlighten parents on reliable methods of bringing up a child in the home.
- Teachers would be beneficiaries of this study because it will enlighten them more on how reliable methods of training/impacting knowledge on students and their children in the home.
- The students will benefit from the study because its finding will help them appreciate the need for parental care, support and positive values given. It will make the children (students) to be more adaptive to parental care.
- The society will undoubtedly benefit from this study because, parental value system has to do with the child's behavior and his/her academic success in the school thus, successful and upright children in the society breeds a safe, profitable and conducive society.
- The government, policy makers and educational planners will benefit from the findings and recommendations of this study in terms of making effective planning/policies that will be beneficial to carter for children (students) of all races/status or socio- economic background of individuals (parents).

1.4 Research questions

The following research questions were formulated as a guide for this study:

- To what extent does the socio-economic level of parents' influence students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?
- To what extent does parental educational level affect students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?
- To what extent do Parent occupation and income affect students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Socioeconomic status of parents

Education not only provides knowledge and skills, but also inculcates values, and training instincts, and fosters the right attitude and habits (Muhammed U.O. and Muhammed N.D., 2010). Again, in their study, they posited that cultural heritage and values are transmitted from one generation to another through Education.

It is not out of place to imagine that parental socioeconomic background can have possible effects on the academic performance of students in Home Economics in junior secondary school. In line with the above assertion, (Hill, Fyan, & Kelly, 2004) also argued that the socioeconomic status of parents does not only affects academic performance, but also makes it possible for children from low backgrounds to compete with their counterparts from high socio-economic backgrounds under the same academic environment (Hill, Fyan, and Kelly, 2004).

(Machebe, 2012), in her research, reported that; parental socioeconomic status could influence the academic performance of students at school (Machebe, 2012).

In Nigeria, (Oni, 2007) and (Omoegun, 2007) averred that there is a significant difference between the rates of deviant behavior among students from high and low socio-economic statuses (Oni, 2007) and (Omoegun, 2007). This assertion is again hinged on the nature of parental socio-economic background. Moreover, (Eze, 1996) opined that a child who gets proper school materials like school uniforms, textbooks, and prompt payment of school fees has the optimal advantage of the full complement of resources offered by a formal learning environment will performs very great. The foregoing discussion established that socioeconomic status and a host of other factors relating to the home environment of students, such as the educational background of parents, health status parental occupation, and family size could have effects on children's academic achievement (Eze, 1996).

Eyake (2003) reported that the students' attitudes to learning and academic performances in Home Economics are shaped by the kind of stimuli offered to them by their various environments. This can be considered in terms of the type of family, the home, parental social orientation, educational level, and occupation to mention but a few. It is, therefore, evident that students' performance is contingent on the stimulus the home offers (Eyake 2003).

(Adesiye, 2001) in his study accessed the percentage recent of secondary school dropouts, it entailed that such students are usually from non-payment of fees, broken homes, wiring polygamous families, or other socially related problems (Adesiye 2001).

Furthermore, the economic position of parents is one of major factors that can greatly influence the educational upbringing of a child. In most families, either or none of the parents may be earning income sufficient enough to sustain the family, faced with malnutrition and other emotional and psychological effects, the mental development of the child would be greatly retarded (Kelly, 2004).

(Orhunger, 2000) adds that a low-income family with plenty of feeding problems may produce children whose physical and mental development poses real challenges to the schools' effort at optimum development of the child (Orhunger, 2000).

2.2. Parental Educational Level

Education has a pivotal role nationally, as well as individual character building. It is a lifeline for any society and nation (Kelly, 2004). The education of a child needs multidimensional efforts. Students, teachers, institute, and parents all have their importance in a child's learning process. On the other hand, parents' education is such a motivating force for a child which paves the way for his/her future Jencks, 2012. It is an admitted fact that the children of educated parents are more confident, resourceful, and experienced than children whose parents lack education. (Orhunger, 2000).

(Jencks, 2012) says that the family plays an important role in formal and informal education. Family characteristics represent several variables like education, income, beliefs, occupation, and size of family also imply the performance of children (Jencks, 2012).

Significant reliable research studies have shown that the socioeconomic status of parents is the best predictor of student academic achievement (Coleman 2006). Again, parental education is considered the most stable aspect of socio-economic status. It has been well-defined that family plays a vital role in a child's academic achievement and development (Cornell & Gross, 2007).

In other words, parents who are well-learned and professionals provide their children with a favorable environment to motivate or encourage them to develop similar interests and perform well in their subject areas. (Orhunger 2010)

Valencia and Renald in their study of 2001 also observed that the level of a parent's education is related to the academic performance of students in home economics tests. From their study, they concluded that parents who are relatively higher in levels of education tend to transmit to their children more culture of the academic they acquired than parents who are illiterates. The study further revealed that parents' positive values attached to education as a function of their educational achievement (Valencia and Renald, 2001).

Wilton's study of 2005 established the significance of the relationship between educational background and academic performance, this was supported by the study of (Bamisiaye and Williams 2001). The family background of two families was observed; the elite and traditional household. The family setup affects the child's degree of verbal behaviors, instruction attitudes, and communication, in turn, affects the child's academic performance in several courses (Wilton, 2005; Bamisiaye & Williams, 2001).

(Nisbet 2007), attributed academic performance at school to the parents' attitudes and their level of educational attainment. The study further reported that children from parents who have a high interest in science subjects tend to imbibe some attitude towards parental professional occupational subjects which affects their academic performance (Nisbet, 2007).

The study by Smart in 2002 reported that in most homes today it is apparent that parents' educational level correlates positively with the academic performance of their children, are more likely to give their children practice in basic science subjects at home, go to school to find out their progress report and assignment records and function as achievement models. (Good and Brophy, 2012) their study also stressed that educated parents usually show interest in their children's academic performance, choose subjects, and meet and collaborate with administrators of secondary schools to ensure their children's rate of seriousness in their studies (Smart, 2002) and (Good & Brophy, 2012).

2.3. Parental occupation/Income level

The word occupation could be defined as what a person does to earn a living. It can be seen as services rendered to receive wage/salary at the end of the services. Having seen what occupation means, therefore occupational roles and property ownership and control are the criteria by which we define social classes. Occupation differs widely as regards their general desirability. The determinant of desirability is the wage or salary, which goes with the job. Other include the nature of the work done, the opportunity for promotion, and working conditions (dangerous dirty, and training work is undesirable).

Classes are unequal to the extent that rewards tend to be cumulative. In other words, the occupations with the highest salaries are the greatest opportunity for personal initiation. For instance, a top civil servant may earn twenty to thirty times as much as his office cleaners and a peasant farmer may earn in a year less than what a member of parliament may earn in work. These inequalities tend to intensify competition for jobs and make educational success a vital importance (Obasi, 2007).

(Aghametu 1994), reported a positive relationship between parental occupational and children's academic achievement. He found out that the type of work one's parents do determines to a large extent whether the child will attend secondary school or not. Parents of relatively socioeconomic classes can provide their children with more opportunities to learn those things that will aid their learning in school (Aghametu, 1994).

Kenneth and Brain (2001) posited that education can be seen as a form of property. The skills and qualifications obtained through formal education can be sold in the labor market and the most highly qualified get the best job. Parents with high income from their occupation generally must put a substantial amount into educating their children to increase their children's chances of educational achievement and success. They further asserted that the best debates to school and study (Kenneth & Brain, 2001).

Children of parents in professional and managerial occupation are much more likely to be successful than children of unskilled manual workers. Supporting this view, (Beth-miner, 2008) opined that children of middle-class families have stimulating homes, perform better in class work, and stay longer in school than children of low-class families (Beth-miner, 2008).

Uche's study postulated that children from well-to-do families are never without food and shelter as food helps in their brain development. They have expensive wear, they are neat and clean, and they are either driven to school in cars or provided with maids or servants who take them to and from school. Unlike the children from low-class families who share the same room, bed, clothes, or even sleep on the bare floor (Uche, 2003).

Writing on the influence of parents' education on the academic performance and achievement of students, (Douglas, 2012) postulated that the father's occupational level adversely affects a young child because it has a direct bearing on him. He further stated that when a child is ashamed of his father's occupation, whether because of the level of work or the type of wear demanded by the work, the child is affected thereby leading to poor performance in his class work (Douglas, 2012).

(Douglas, 2012) in his research compared children from working middle-class families who are educated and know the importance of birth control methods and this can control the number of children they have. He further argued that many working-class parents are ignorant of birth control methods and so cannot prevent unwanted conception and babies. In other words, Douglas associated large families of low class. He further argued that working-class (low-class) parents know leaves about healthcare and so do not give their children appropriate healthcare (Douglas, 2012).

(Heagin, 2005) associated low-class families with poor health and generally associated large families and poor health with poor academic performance in their children. He concluded that these groups of children generally achieve less in school than children from middle-class families.

(Payne, 1998) believes that students from poverty lack the cognitive strategies needed to be successful in the educational system. (Conger and Elder, 1994) assert that families at a variety of income levels who suffer economic stress of any kind are more likely than families that are not economically stressed to experience depression, marital clashes and be harsh with their children which points to the fact that, poverty and economic stress are associated with parent-child conflict which leads to poorer grades and weakens emotional and social growth. The study by Klebanor reported that the disparity in the home learning environment of higher and lower-income children is a reason for nearly half of the effect of income on the achievement scores of preschool children (Klebanor, 2002).

Similarly, good parenting supported by a strong economic home background could enhance the strong academic performance of the child. This further predicts academic performance when the child is properly counseled in the choice of his/her courses and vocation that matches his mental ability, interest, and capability whereas the children in the care of the illiterate mothers will find themselves roaming about the street laboring to make ends meet. (Danesy and Okediran, 2002) lamented that street hawking among young school students has psychologically imposed other problems, like sex networking behavior, and juvenile delinquent behavior, which takes much of the student's school time that necessitates poor academic performance and dropout syndrome noticed among young school students. Nevertheless, they also lamented that the maternal and paternal deprivation of the essential needs of young students has prompted their poor performance in public examinations, such as JSSCE, WASC, and NECO (Danesy & Okediran, 2002).

2.4. Summary of literature review

One of the key inhibitors identified here is poor parental influence, that is, where the parents are not economically buoyant, they will be unable to provide the essential needs in aid of the child's learning and these will have a drastic effect on their children's learning. Parental economic class affects the choice of schools for their sons and daughters and how well their needs are responded to will boost the self-ego the learners carry to school. Among the inhibitors also highlighted are poor parental level of education and poor home discipline. Well-educated parents provide for their children with a model of academic background to build upon. They also have all that is required to aid, supervise, and direct the children in academic matters (Klebanor, 2002).

Poor parental education is a syndrome. No matter how well an illiterate parent loves and cares for his children, he cannot give them what he does not have. Poor parental background is an inhibitor to the child's learning. For one, when the child works on his school assignment at home, and encounters a problem, he naturally would look up the parents for assistance which may not materialize. (Klebanor, 2002).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design

The design employed for the study was a correlational research design. This design is a type of design that involves observing two variables in order to establish a satisfactory corresponding relationship between them (Ofo, 2002). The design tries to identify variables that have some sort of relationship to the extent that a change in one creates some change in the other. This design was considered appropriate in this study since the aimed to investigate and determine the relationship between the variables. The degree of relationship between the two variables is classified in the form of correlation coefficient. R. (Creswell, 2013) penned down that in a correlational research that the researcher uses correlation test to describe and measure the magnitude and direction of association or relationship between two or more variables or sets or scores.

3.2. Area of study

The area of the study is Calabar Municipality which is a Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is one of the oldest local government area in Cross River State. It has an area of 142 km² and a population of 179,392 at the 2006 census. The postal code of the area is 540. Calabar Municipality lied between latitude 04° 15' and 5° 15 North of the Equator and longitude 8° 25' and 7° 05' East of the Greenwich Meridian. In the North, the Municipal is bounded by Odukpani Local Government Area, in the North-East by the great Kwa River. Its Southern shores are bounded by the Calabar River and Calabar South Local Government Area; while the Atlantic Ocean is on the West. It has an area of 331.551 square kilometers.

Calabar Municipality plays a dual role. Apart from being the Capital city of Cross River State, it also plays its role as headquarters of the Southern Senatorial District. There are ten wards in the municipal. Two ethnic groups form the indigenous population. These are the Quas and the Efiks. However, because of its cosmopolitan status, there abound people from all parts of the state and Nigeria in the city. By virtue of its location along the waterfront, the Efiks embraced Western culture. They carried on successful trade with early Europeans. Fishing is another occupation identified with them. The Quas on the other hand occupy the bulk of the hinterland of Calabar where farmers, hunters, traders and blacksmiths are found. Efik language is the major language, although English language serves as a lingua franca among the inhabitants. The major occupations of the people are fishing, farming, trading, craft work, while a few are civil and public servants.

The municipal has three levels of health facilities, among which are a Teaching hospital, Nigerian Navy Reference Hospital, Primary Health Care facilities and a large number of private hospitals. There are many educational establishments among which are both private and public primary schools, private, missionary and government owned secondary schools and including higher institution like University of Calabar which is one of the prominent second generation Universities in Nigeria.

The Municipality hosted the first competitive football, cricket and field hockey games in Nigeria. The Municipality has an international Museum, a botanical garden, a free trade zone and port, an international airport and sea port and integrated sports stadium complex, a garment factory, rice industry and so on. Calabar Municipality houses the seat of government with many industries like flower Mill, Nigeria Port Authority, Banks, private and public enterprises. The Municipality is a unique centre regarding its high degree of urbanism compared with the surrounding local government areas such as Akpabuyo, Odukpani and Calabar South.

3.3. Study Population

The study population comprises senior secondary school students (SSS) in sixteen public secondary schools in Calabar Municipal of Cross River State. The SSS students were considered for this study because majority of these students offered Home Economics as a general subject. The total population is one thousand, eight-hundred and forty (1,840) students, out of this population, 822 are male, students and 1018 are female students (Department of Planning, Research & Statistics, Cross River Ministry of Education, 2020). The detail is presented in Table 1 below. The study population consisted of Senior Secondary School students in Calabar Metropolis.

3.4. Sample and Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting six (6) public secondary schools out of fifteen public secondary schools in Calabar municipality of Cross River State, Nigeria. The six public Secondary Schools were selected through balloting with replacement. Here, the names of the fifteen public secondary schools that constitute the target population of the study on slips of papers (ballots) was written. These ballot papers were put into a can and thoroughly mixed up. Then, with eyes closed, a piece of paper representing a school as already labelled was blindly picked. This ballot was returned into the can, reshuffled to mix up and then another picking was done, the schools picked was noted and returned to the can. This process was repeated until six (6) schools out of the fifteen public secondary schools in the study area were picked. In this way, six (6) public secondary schools were chosen.

Table 1 Distribution of Study Population

S/No.	Name of School	M	F	Total
1	Army Day Secondary School, Eburutu Barracks	48	55	103
2	Estate Secondary School, Ikot Ansa	45	51	96
3	West African People's Institute, Diamond Hill	50	59	109
4	Government College, Ikot Ansa	47	60	107
5	Government Secondary School, Federal Housing Estate	56	58	114
6	Government Secondary School, State Housing Estate	58	50	108
7	Government Secondary School, Akim Qua	65	64	129
8	Government Girls' Secondary School, Big Qua	-	129	129
9	Government Secondary School, Ikot Effanga Mkpa	64	66	130
10	Government Secondary School, Nyaghasang	63	76	139
11	Government Secondary School, Barracks Road	64	74	138
12	Government Secondary School, , Nasarawa	48	65	113
13	Margaret Ekpo Secondary School, IBB Way	44	45	89
14	NYSC Model Secondary School	56	56	112

15	Special Education Centre, Big Qua	46	55	101
16	Government Secondary School, Akai Efa	68	55	123
	Total	822	1018	1840

Source: Department of Planning, Research & Statistics, Cross River Ministry of Education, 2017

3.5. Instrument for data collection

The instrument used to get data for the research is a questionnaire and Home Economics Achievement test (HEAT). The questionnaire is divided into two sections, A" and B". Section "A" consists of the personal data of the respondent, while section "B" is the questionnaire items indicating: Agreed (A) Disagreed (D), which the respondents are required to tick the category that best suits their opinion. The Home Economics Achievement test (HEAT) which is the second instrument of this study contains fifty (50) items with A-D options for testing measured students' academic performance in Home Economics, and each of the correct answer carried '2 marks'. This instrument was developed by the researcher with the aid of table of specifications in order to ensure content validity of the test (see Table 2).

Table 2 Home Economic table of specification

Unit	Subject content	%	Knowledge (38%)	Comprehensive (38%)	Application (12%)	Analysis (12%)	Total
1	Food and nutrition	40	6	6	2	2	16
2	Clothing and textile	30	5	5	2	1	13
3	Housing and interior design	20	4	4	2	1	11
4	Family and economics	10	4	3	2	1	10
		100	19	18	8	5	50

3.5.1. Validation of the instrument

The face and content validity of the instruments was achieved by surrendering the instruments to three lecturers in measurement and evaluation to make their inputs in terms of adding more relevant items and removing irrelevant ones, and making any other appropriate suggestions to improve the quality of the items. Their corrections and suggestions were considered by the researcher and the instruments were given approval for trial testing to establish the psychometric properties.

3.5.2. Reliability of the instrument

To ascertain the reliability of the instruments, a pilot study was done in two secondary schools in Calabar South local government area which is outside the study area. Forty copies of the instruments each were distributed and retrieved. The reliability of the instrument HEAT was established using Kuder-Richardson K-R-20 formula. The internal consistency of HEAT yielded 0.80, which showed that the instrument was appropriate to measure what it purport to measure (see Tables 3).

Table 3 Reliability of students' Home Economics achievement test items using Kuder Richardson formula K-R-20

Variable	No. of items	Σpq	Sx^2	r_{xy}
Home Economics performance	40	6.15	102.1	0.81

3.6. Procedure for data collection

Before the actual data collection, the researcher visited the selected public secondary schools in Calabar municipality to seek permission to have access to the students. Within the space of seven days, and thereafter, the researcher with her team embarks on data collection using the two research instruments, questionnaire and Home Economic Achievement Test (HEAT). The two instruments were administered in-person with help of the class teachers. The exercise lasted for two months.

A total of 249 of the instruments were administered to the respondents in the sampled public secondary schools. The items on the questionnaire were carefully read out and explained to the understanding of the respondent who subsequently filled in their appropriate response. At the end of the exercise, all the distributed instruments were retrieved and fully completed. Therefore, the instruments were adjudged useful for data analysis.

3.7. Data preparation/scoring

To prepare the data that were collected for statistical analysis on parental influence on Home Economics Study and SSS students, a coding formula was designed to code the response of respondents. The instruments were appropriately coded and scored. Items under instructional materials availability and Instructional materials usage checklists were coded as follows:

- SA- representing Strongly Agreed - 5 points
- A - Representing Agreed - 4 points
- U - Undecided - 3 points
- D - Representing Strongly Disagreed - 2 points
- SD - representing Disagreed - 1 point

3.8. Method of data analysis

The simple average percentage merged with Mean and Standard deviation descriptive statistics was used as a statistical tool for the data analysis. This was to ensure appropriate interpretation of the data collected during the phase of distribution of study questionnaires and HEAT.

4. Results

4.1. Research question one

To what extent does the socio-economic level of parents' influence students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

The question was analyzed using simple percentages merged with mean and standard deviation descriptive statistical tools and the results presented in table 4.

Table 4 To what extent does the Socio- economic level of parents influence students' Academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Remark
1.	My parent are educated and they usually advise me on the study of home economics?	480 (26.1%)	389 (21.1%)	101 (5.5%)	260 (14.1%)	610 (33.2%)	2.93	1.65	Disagree
2.	Does either of your parents' job motivate you to study Home Economics?	520 (28.3%)	370 (20.1%)	98 (5.3%)	459 (24.9%)	393 (21.4%)	3.09	1.56	Agreed
3.	Children of educated parent always perform well, studying Home Economics?	610 (33.2%)	332 (18%)	46 (2.5%)	356 (19.3%)	496 (27%)	3.11	1.66	Agreed
4.	Do your parent assist you in doing your homework?	736 (40%)	552 (30%)	52 (2.8%)	132 (7.2%)	368 (20%)	3.63	1.54	Agreed

N=1,840, Five point's likert scale ratings:SA = 5, A = 4, U = 3, D = 2, SD = 1. Criterion mean = 3.00. Percentages of the respondents' responses are the figures enclosed in braces

4.2. Research question two

To what extent does parental educational level affect students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

In like manner, the question was analyzed using simple percentages merged with mean and standard deviation descriptive statistical tools and the results presented in table 5.

Table 5 To what extent does parents' educational level affect students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Remark
5.	Does your parent assist you in doing your homework?	533 (29%)	626 (34%)	20 (1.1%)	300 (16.3%)	361 (19.6%)	3.36	1.52	Agreed
6	Are your parents educated?	662 (36%)	626 (34%)	42 (2.3%)	335 (18.2%)	175 (9.5%)	3.69	1.37	Agreed
7.	Do your parents care if you fail exams?	871 (47.3%)	547 (29.7%)	22 (1.2%)	224 (12.2%)	176 (9.6%)	3.93	1.35	Agreed
8.	Do your parents attend your school functions?	230 (12.5%)	268 (14.6%)	54 (2.9%)	848 (46.1%)	440 (23.9%)	2.46	1.33	Disagreed

N=1,840, Five points likert scale ratings: SA = 5, A = 4, U = 3, D = 2, SD = 1. Criterion mean = 3.00. Percentages of the respondents' responses are the figures enclosed in braces.

4.3. Research question three

To what extent do Parent occupation and income affect students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

The question was analyzed using simple percentages merged with mean and standard deviation descriptive statistical tools and the results is as presented in table 6.

Table 6 To what extent does Parent occupation and income affect students' academic performance in Calabar Metropolis?

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Remark
9.	Do your parents visit you in school?	230 (12.5%)	268 (14.6%)	54 (2.9%)	848 (46.1%)	440 (23.9%)	2.46	1.33	Disagreed
10.	Do you think your parent can sponsor you successfully?	658 (35.8%)	546 (29.7%)	38 (2.1%)	106 (5.8%)	492 (26.7%)	3.42	1.64	Agreed
11	The financial problem in your home is caused by large number of people living there?	856 (46.5%)	475 (25.8%)	34 (1.8%)	339 (18.4%)	136 (7.4%)	3.86	1.37	Agreed
12	Do your parents assist with your study at home?	238 (12.9%)	456 (24.8%)	65 (3.5%)	440 (23.9%)	641 (34.8%)	2.57	1.48	Disagreed

N=1,840, Five points likert scale ratings: SA = 5, A = 4, U = 3, D = 2, SD = 1. Criterion mean = 3.00. Percentages of the respondents' responses are the figures enclosed in braces.

4.4. Interpretation/Discussion of results

4.4.1. Research Question One

The table 4 presents results on the extent to which students perceived the influence of their parents' socioeconomic level on their academic performance in Home Economics in Calabar Metropolis. The results showed that for most items, the respondents generally agreed that their parents' education level or occupation had a significant impact on their performance in this subject. Specifically, the students disagreed that educated parents advise them on Home Economics (mean=2.93). However, they agreed that their parents' jobs motivate them to study the subject (mean=3.09), and that children of educated parents always perform well in it (mean=3.11). Furthermore, they also agreed that their parents assist them with homework (mean=3.63). Overall, the results suggest that factors other than parental socioeconomic

status may play a more significant role in determining academic performance in Home Economics for these students. This inferences were drawn following the criterion mean of (3.00).

These findings have supported the research study conducted by (James, 2014) who found that “if there is only little parental involvement in a child education, there is more of a likelihood that the student will not succeed”. Then the cause of pupils’ poor performance in in school therefore appears to arise partly from the socio-economic status.

(Good and Brophy, 2012) their study also stressed that educated parents usually show interest in their children's academic performance, choose subjects, meet and collaborate with administrators of secondary schools to ensure their children's rate of seriousness in their studies (Smart, 2002; and Good & Brophy, 2012).

4.4.2. Research Question Two

The table 5 presents showed results on the extent to which students perceive their parents' educational level affects their academic performance in Calabar Metropolis. The responses are given on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD).

For item 5, "Does your parent assist you in doing your homework?" the mean score of (3.36) suggests that respondents agreed with this statement. This could imply that many parents actively assist their children with homework, regardless of their educational level.

Item 6, "Are your parents educated?" had a mean of (3.69), indicating that respondents generally agreed that their parents are educated. This suggests a significant portion of the sample had parents with some level of formal education.

Respondents vehemently agreed (mean = 3.93) with item 7, "Do your parents care if you fail exams?" suggesting that most parents, educated or not, care about their children's academic performance and potential failure in exams.

However, for item 8, "Do your parents attend your school functions?" the mean score of 2.46 implies that respondents disagreed with this statement. This could mean that despite caring about their children's academic performance, many parents may not actively attend school functions, possibly due to other commitments or priorities.

(Douglas, 2012) in his research compared children from working middle-class families who are educated and know the importance of birth control methods and this can control the number of children they have. He further argued that many working-class parents are ignorant of birth control methods and so cannot prevent unwanted conception and babies. In other words, Douglas associated large families of low class. He further argued that working-class (low-class) parents know leaves about healthcare and so do not give their children appropriate healthcare (Douglas, 2012).

4.4.3. Research Question Three

The table 6 presents results of data on the extent to which students perceive their parents' occupation and income affect their academic performance in Calabar Metropolis.

For item 9, "Do your parents visit you in school?", the mean score of 2.46 suggests that respondents generally disagreed, indicating that many parents may not visit their children in school regularly, possibly due to work commitments or other factors.

Regarding item 10, "Do you think your parent can sponsor you successfully?" the mean score of 3.42 shows that respondents accepted or agreed, implying that students perceived their parents not having financial constraints in fully sponsoring their education.

Item 11, "The financial problem in your home is caused by a large number of people living there," had a mean of 3.86, suggesting that respondents agreed with this statement. This could indicate that larger household sizes and the associated financial burdens may contribute to perceived financial problems at home.

For item 12, "Do your parents assist with your study at home?", the mean score of 2.57 indicates that respondents generally disagreed, suggesting that parental assistance with studies at home may be limited, potentially due to work commitments or other factors.

Children of parents in professional and managerial occupation are much more likely to be successful than children of unskilled manual workers. Supporting this view, (Beth-miner, 2008) opined that children of middle-class families have

stimulating homes, perform better in class work, and stay longer in school than children of low-class families (Bethminer, 2008).

(Heagin, 2005) associated low-class families with poor health and generally associated large families and poor health with poor academic performance in their children. He concluded that these groups of children generally achieve less in school than children from middle-class families.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated Parental influence' on Academic Performance of Home Economic Students in Senior Secondary Students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State – Nigeria. The result of the study revealed that low income of parent's is a major impediment to academic success and development in home economics on the part of the students. Secondly students' academic performance in Home Economics is predicted by a chain of socio-economic factors resident in parent's and family network.

Generally, while a significant portion of the respondents reported having educated parents who care about their academic performance. Factors such as parental involvement in homework assistance and attendance at school functions may play a more significant role in influencing academic outcomes. Again, these generalizations were drawn on the basis that the criterion mean is (3.00).

Overall, the results suggest that students perceived their parents' occupation and income as potential barriers to their academic performance, with factors such as financial constraints, larger household sizes, and limited parental assistance at home being identified as potential challenges. However, it is important to note that these perceptions may vary among individuals, and other factors, such as school quality, individual student characteristics, and overall socioeconomic status, may also play a role in academic performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby proffered.

- Firstly, on the account of families of low socio-economic status who cannot afford to train their children properly in school, the government should increase allocation of funds to provide for more amenities to facilitate learning in the school so that these poor student's will not lack basic amenities in the school.
- Parents' should be sensitized on the need to make education of their children and wards a priority in the face of the present economic predicament by adequately providing for their school materials with the meagre resources they have.
- Counsellors should provide the necessary assistance and psychological support for this poor student's whose emotional and psychological stability have been shattered by poverty.
- Local and international Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO's) and other stakeholders in education should be sensitized to weld support of the findings of secondary school projects in Nigeria most especially in the research area.
- Parents should endeavour to devote some time to supervise their children's academic progress.
- Parents should try and provide the basic Home Economics learning materials for their children.
- Parents should encourage their children to study Home Economics.
- Parents should endeavour to pay their children school fees in time, not waiting until they are drove.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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